

Recovering metals and mineral fraction
from steelmaking residues

Deliverable 2.3

	Name	Signature and Date
Prepared by:	Wolfgang Reiter	
Checked by:	Tamara Tappeiner	
Approved by:	Johannes Rieger	

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Table of Content

Abstract	6
1 Introduction.....	7
2 BOF and EAF dusts	8
2.1 BOF dusts	8
2.2 EAF dusts	9
3 Required documents	10
3.1 Transport documents	10
3.2 Confirmation of receipt of the products of the RecoDust process	10
4 References.....	11

List of Figures

Figure 1: Formation of BOFD [1]..... 8

Abbreviations and acronyms

RDS	RecoDust slag
CZO	Crude zinc oxide
BOF	Basix oxygen furnace
EAF	Electric arc furnace
BOFD	Basic oxygen furnace dust
EAFD	Electric arc furnace dust

Abstract

This document details the deliverable D2.3 "Fulfilled legal requirements to import BOF and / or EAF dusts to Austria". Basic oxygen furnace dust (BOFD) and electric arc furnace dust (EAFD) are declared as hazardous waste due a commission decision Document 02000D0532-20150601. This document strictly regulates the transportation from one country to another.

For the import of BOFD and EAFD, public authorities from both countries need to be involved.

The documents

- Movement document for Austria (AT 036663)
- Notification document for Austria (AT 036663)

need to be filled. Also, the confirmation of the disposal of the resulting RecoDust products (RecoDust slag (RDS), crude zinc oxide (CZO)) from the company "Saubermacher Dienstleistungs AG" is necessary for the legal movement of the BOFD or EAFD to Austria. The company Saubermacher Dienstleistungs AG supports the project partners Montanuniversitaet Leoben (Chair of Thermal Processing Technology) and K1-MET in properly disposing the RecoDust products after they are not used anymore.

1 Introduction

This document represents the requirements of the RecoDust process both in terms of inputs and operational parameters of the ReMFra project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058362.

The feedstock of the RecoDust process must meet the requirements described in Deliverable D2.2. This feedstock is declared as hazardous waste due the commission decision Document 02000D0532-20150601. The transportation from one country to another is strictly regulated. The current document describes the needed steps and documents for the transportation.

2 BOF and EAF dusts

BOFD and EAFD are by-products by the production of steel. The scrap rate used in the basic oxygen furnace (BOF) is about 25 wt.-% and the scrap rate used in the electric arc furnace (EAF) is up to 100 wt.-%.

2.1 BOF dusts

The BOFD are formed during blowing the oxygen through a lance over the molten pig iron inside the BOF converter. The main mechanism of dust generation is the so-called bubble bursting, which is shown in Figure 1. This reaction spontaneously forms carbon monoxide bubbles in the steel bath and is crucial for the speed of the BOF process as it provides excellent bath agitation and mixing. Once formed in the molten iron at the extremely high temperatures, these bubbles are forced upward before reaching the surface due to their relative density (a). Once at the surface of the hot metal, the upper part of the bubble thins (b) until the surface tension can no longer hold back the hot gas, which separates from the liquid and escapes into the atmosphere (c). The resulting high pressure at the edges of the now burst bubble (d) forms a jet (e) that ejects droplets of molten iron from the melt (f). The other mechanism is the vaporisation of metals and elements, like zinc, lead, and chlorine and the entrainment of charged material.

Figure 1: Formation of BOFD [1]

2.2 EAF dusts

EAFD is produced when zinc bearing scrap is remelted in the EAF. The type of used scrap has a huge influence on the dust composition and properties. The mechanism of dust formation is near the same as BOFD formation, through bubble bursting and the evaporation of volatile components.

3 Required documents

In this chapter, the required documents are described for a transport of steelmaking dusts to the RecoDust pilot plant located in Austria.

3.1 Transport documents

For the legal import of BOF or EAF dust to Austria, public authorities from both countries (Austria as well as the country from which the dust originates) need to be involved. A contract between the two parties is needed regarding to “Article 5 of Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2006 on shipments of waste.

Two documents must be fulfilled:

- Movement document for Austria (AT 036663)
- Notification document for Austria (AT 036663)

Both documents can be found in the appendix.

3.2 Confirmation of receipt of the products of the RecoDust process

Both products of the RecoDust process, the RDS and the CZO, must be properly disposed after treating the imported steelmaking dusts. It must be ensured that the two products RDS and CZO are properly disposed according to the following waste designation:

Schl. Nr. 31218 Elektroofenschlacke (German for „electric furnace slag”)

Schl. Nr. 31217 Filterstäube, NE-metallhaltig (German for „filter dusts, containing nonferrous metals“)

If, for any reason, the disposal of the RDS and the CZO is not possible, the Chair of Thermal Processing Technology from Montanuniversitaet Leoben has the possibility for a storage of RDS and CZO for 90 days without any further costs.

4 References

1. Stewart, D.J.; Barron, A.R. Pyrometallurgical removal of zinc from basic oxygen steelmaking dust – A review of best available technology. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* **2020**, *157*, 104746, doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104746.

Appendix

Movement document for transboundary movements/shipments of waste

1. Corresponding to notification No: AT 036663		2. Serial/total number of shipments: /	
3. Exporter - notifier Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail:		4. Importer - consignee Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail:	
6. Actual quantity: Tonnes (Mg): m³:		8. Actual date of shipment:	
7. Packaging type(s) (1):		Number of packages:	
Special handling requirements (2):		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	
8.(a) 1st carrier (3): Registration No: Name: Address: Tel: Fax: E-mail:		8.(b) 2nd carrier (3): Registration No: Name: Address: Tel: Fax: E-mail:	8.(c) Last carrier (3): Registration No: Name: Address: Tel: Fax: E-mail:
----- To be completed by carrier's representative -----			
Means of transport(1): Date of transfer: Signature:		Means of transport(1): Date of transfer: Signature:	Means of transport(1): Date of transfer: Signature:
9. Waste generator(s)/producer(s) (4)(5)(6): Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail: Site of generation (2):		12. Designation and composition of the waste (2):	
10. Disposal facility <input type="checkbox"/> or recovery facility <input type="checkbox"/> Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail: Actual site of disposal/recovery (2):		13. Physical characteristics (1):	
11. Disposal/recovery operation(s) D-Code / R-Code (1):		14. Waste identification (fill in relevant codes) (i) Basel Annex VIII (or IX if applicable): (ii) OECD code (if different from i): (iii) EC list of wastes: (iv) National code in country of export: (v) National code in country of import: (vi) Other (specify): (vii) Y-code: (viii) H-code (1): (ix) UN Class (1): (x) UN number: (xi) UN shipping name: (xii) Customs code(s) (HS):	
15. Exporter's - notifiers's/generator's - producer's declaration(4): I certify that the above information is complete and correct to my best knowledge. I also certify that legally enforceable written contractual obligations have been entered into, that any applicable insurance or other financial guarantee is in force covering the transboundary movement and that all necessary consents have been received from the competent authorities of the countries concerned. Name: Date: Signature:			
18. For use by any person involved in the transboundary movement in case additional information is required:			
17. Shipment received by importer - consignee (if not facility): Name: Date: Signature:			
TO BE COMPLETED BY DISPOSAL/RECOVERY FACILITY			
18. Shipment received at disposal facility <input type="checkbox"/> or recovery facility <input type="checkbox"/> Date of reception: Accepted: <input type="checkbox"/> Rejected: <input type="checkbox"/> Quantity received: Tonnes (Mg): m³: * Immediately contact competent authorities Approximate date of disposal/recovery: Disposal/recovery operation (1): Name: Date: Signature:		18. I certify that the disposal/recovery of the waste described above has been completed. Name: Date: Signature and stamp:	

(1) See list of abbreviations and codes on the next page

(2) Attach details if necessary

(3) If more than three carriers, attach information as required in blocks 8 (a, b, c)

(4) Required by the Basel Convention

(5) Attach list if more than one

(6) If required by national legislation

Notification document for transboundary movements/shipments of waste

1. Exporter - notifier Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail:		3. Notification No: AT 036663 Notification concerning A. (i) Individual shipment: <input type="checkbox"/> (ii) Multiple shipments: <input type="checkbox"/> B. (i) Disposal (1): <input type="checkbox"/> (ii) Recovery: <input type="checkbox"/> C. Pre-consented recovery facility (2)(3) Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>													
2. Importer - consignee Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail:		4. Total intended number of shipments: 5. Total intended quantity (4): Tonnes (Mg): m³:													
8. Intended carrier(s) Registration No: Name (7): Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail: Means of transport (5):		6. Intended period of time for shipment(s) (4): First departure: Last departure: 7. Packaging type(s) (5): Special handling requirements (5): Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>													
9. Waste generator(s)/producer(s) (1)(7)(8) Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail: Site and process of generation (5):		11. Disposal/recovery operation(s) (2): D-Code / R-Code (5): Technology employed (5): Reason for export (1)(5):													
10. Disposal facility (2): <input type="checkbox"/> or recovery facility (2): <input type="checkbox"/> Registration No: Name: Address: Contact person: Tel: Fax: E-mail: Actual site of disposal/recovery:		12. Designation and composition of the waste (5): 13. Physical characteristics (5): 14. Waste identification (fill in relevant codes) (i) Basel Annex VIII (or IX if applicable): (ii) OECD code (if different from i): (iii) EC list of wastes: (iv) National code in country of export: (v) National code in country of import: (vi) Other (specify): (vii) Y-code (5): (viii) H-code (5): (ix) UN Class (5): (x) UN number: (xi) UN shipping name: (xii) Customs code(s) (HS):													
15. (a) Countries/states concerned, (b) code No of competent authorities where applicable, (c) specific points of exit or entry (border crossing or port) <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>State of export/dispatch</th> <th>State(s) of transit (entry and exit)</th> <th>State of import/destination</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>(a)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>(b)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>(c)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				State of export/dispatch	State(s) of transit (entry and exit)	State of import/destination	(a)			(b)			(c)		
State of export/dispatch	State(s) of transit (entry and exit)	State of import/destination													
(a)															
(b)															
(c)															
16. Customs offices of entry and/or exit and/or export: (European Community) Entry: Exit: Export:															
17. Exporter's - notifier's/generator's - producer's (1) declaration: I certify that the information is complete and correct to my best knowledge. I also certify that legally enforceable written contractual obligations have been entered into and that any applicable insurance or other financial guarantee is or shall be in force covering the transboundary movement. Exporter's/notifier's name: Date: Signature: Generator's/producer's name: Date: Signature:			18. Number of annexes attached:												
FOR USE BY COMPETENT AUTHORITIES															
19. Acknowledgement from the relevant competent authority of countries of import - destination/transit (1) / export - dispatch (8): Country: Notification received on: Acknowledgement sent on: Name of competent authority: Stamp and/or signature:		20. Written consent (1)(8) to the movement provided by the competent authority of (Country) : Consent given on: _____ until: _____ Consent valid from: _____ Specific conditions: No <input type="checkbox"/> If Yes, see block 21 (5): <input type="checkbox"/> Name of competent authority: Stamp and/or signature:													
21. Specific conditions on consenting to the movement or reasons for objecting:															

(1) Required by the Basel Convention
 (2) In the case of an R12/R13 or D13-D15 operation, also attach corresponding information on any subsequent R12/R13 or D13-D15 facilities and on the subsequent R1-R11 or D1-D12 facility/ies when required
 (3) To be completed for movements within the OECD area and only if B3) applies
 (4) Attach detailed list if multiple shipments
 (5) See list of abbreviations and codes on the next page
 (6) Attach details if necessary
 (7) Attach list if more than one
 (8) If required by national legislation
 (9) If applicable under the OECD Decision